

Main Learning Theories in Education

Georgios Giannoukos ✉
Second Chance School, Greece

Abstract

Six major learning theories explain how people acquire knowledge and skills: behaviorism focuses on how environmental stimuli and consequences shape observable behaviors; cognitivism emphasizes internal mental processes and representations; constructivism highlights learners actively constructing their own understanding; humanism stresses personal experiences, values, and motivations; connectionism emphasizes neural networks and distributed representations; and sociocultural learning theory which according to this theory, learning takes place through collaborative activities with others, where individuals build upon their existing knowledge and skills. These influential theories have impacted educational practices and sparked ongoing debates as researchers and practitioners grapple with the complexity of learning.

Keywords: *learning theories, behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism, humanism, connectionism, sociocultural learning theory.*

Suggested citation: Giannoukos, G. (2024). Main Learning Theories in Education. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(5), 93-100. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(5).06

Introduction

There are several learning theories that have been proposed to explain how people acquire knowledge and skills. Some of the most influential theories are: 1. Behaviorism: This theory, developed by psychologists such as Ivan Pavlov and B.F. Skinner, focuses on observable behaviors and how they are shaped by environmental stimuli and consequences. According to behaviorism, learning occurs through a process of conditioning, in which a response to a stimulus is reinforced or punished, leading to the strengthening or weakening of the behavior. 2. Cognitivism: This theory, developed by psychologists such as Jean Piaget and Noam Chomsky, emphasizes the role of mental processes and internal representations in learning. According to cognitivism, learning involves the acquisition of knowledge and skills through the manipulation of mental representations, such as symbols and concepts, in the mind. 3. Constructivism: This theory, developed by psychologists such as Lev Vygotsky and Jean Piaget, emphasizes the active role of the learner in constructing their own understanding of the world. According to constructivism, learning occurs through a process of assimilating new information into existing knowledge structures, and accommodating these structures to fit new experiences. 4. Humanism: This theory,

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

developed by psychologists such as Carl Rogers and Abraham Maslow, emphasizes the importance of the learner's personal experiences, values, and motivations in learning. According to humanism, learning is a holistic process that involves the integration of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains, and is facilitated by a supportive and empowering learning environment. 5. Connectionism: This theory, developed by psychologists such as David Rumelhart and Geoffrey Hinton, emphasizes the role of neural networks and distributed representations in learning. According to connectionism, learning involves the strengthening or weakening of connections between neurons in the brain, leading to the formation of complex patterns of activity that represent knowledge and skills. 6. Sociocultural learning theory: The sociocultural theory highlights the significance of social interaction in shaping individuals' cognitive growth. According to this theory, human learning is primarily influenced by social factors, and one's cognitive abilities are shaped by their interactions with others in their environment. Based on the sociocultural theory, individuals' psychological growth is influenced to some extent by mentors in their lives, including caregivers and educators. Additionally, engaging in social and cultural activities contributes to the personal development of individuals' beliefs and values. Consequently, this theory underscores the impact of peers and mentors on individual learning, as well as the significance of people's attitudes and cultural beliefs in shaping their learning experiences. These theories have influenced educational practice in various ways, from the design of instructional materials and teaching strategies to the development of assessment and evaluation methods. They have also led to ongoing debates and controversies, as researchers and practitioners grapple with the complex and multifaceted nature of learning.

Behaviorism

The concept of learning, according to this theory, is a product of a sequence of associations between stimuli and responses. Learning is a modification in the behavior of the learner, and the crucial aspect is to describe it rather than to explain it. J.B Watson, I. Pavlov, E.D. Thorndike, and B.F. Skinner are the academics who support this theory, which is also known as behaviorism or directed teaching. Pavlov's research on dogs' reflexes (Pavlov, 1992) established the foundation for the theory of classical conditioning, while Watson's experiments on human subjects led him to conclude that learning is a process of conditioning reflexes (Watson, 1924). Thorndike believed that learning can only occur through trial and error and that the relationship between cause and effect is strongly linked (Associationism) (Thorndike, 1931). Skinner (1968) proposed that learning can be achieved by adopting a behavior that is reinforced, which is the fundamental concept of operant conditioning.

Behaviorism is a psychological theory that focuses on studying observable behaviors and how they are acquired and changed through environmental influences like rewards and punishments. Rather than examining internal mental processes like thoughts and emotions, behaviorists believe that comprehending external factors that shape actions allows them to develop successful interventions and treatments for psychological issues. Core principles of behaviorism are learning through experience, conditioning via either rewards or punishments, reinforcement through positive or negative consequences, extinction by removing those consequences, and observational learning by watching others. Behaviorists apply techniques like positive and negative reinforcement to alter behaviors. While behaviorism has been utilized across various domains, critics argue that overlooking complex mental processes and emotions limits

understanding of behavior and reduces efficacy in addressing intricate psychological problems.

Core principles of behaviorism are:

- Learning is the process of acquiring new knowledge and skills through experience, study, and observation.
- Behaviors are learned through conditioning - associating a behavior with a rewarding or punishing consequence to strengthen or weaken it.
- Reinforcement strengthens behaviors by providing positive consequences when the desired behavior occurs.
- Punishment weakens behaviors by applying negative consequences when unwanted behaviors occur.
- Extinction weakens behaviors by removing any rewarding consequences that previously maintained the behavior.
- Observational learning involves acquiring knowledge by observing and imitating others' behaviors and the consequences.

While behaviorism has been applied in fields like education, psychology, and business to develop teaching methods, behavior modification, and marketing strategies, critics argue it overlooks internal mental processes and emotions that are key to understanding behavior and addressing complex psychological issues.

Cognitivism

Cognitivism, a theoretical perspective in psychology, emphasizes the role of mental processes and structures in learning and behavior. In contrast to behaviorism's focus on observable behaviors and reinforcement, cognitivism proposes that people actively construct knowledge and understanding of the world through cognitive processes like perception, attention, memory, and problem-solving (Bandura, 2009). By highlighting these internal mental activities, cognitivism has deeply influenced education, spurring the creation of instructional design theories and active learning strategies that promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Cognitive learning strategies encompass a range of techniques that can be employed by educators and learners to enhance the learning process. These strategies aim to facilitate the storage of acquired knowledge in long-term memory, thereby contributing to the development of a comprehensive knowledge base. To ensure the effectiveness of these strategies, it is crucial to have a clear understanding of the task at hand and the type of learning required (Kurt, 2023).

By employing these cognitive learning strategies at different stages of the learning cycle, educators and learners can enhance the conceptualization of new knowledge and foster a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Constructivism

The theory of Constructivism posits that individuals can acquire knowledge through the process of discovering and solving problems. The primary objective of education

is to facilitate the enhancement and enrichment of one's knowledge. Esteemed scholars such as J. Dewey, L. Vygotsky, J. Piaget, J. Bruner, S. Papert, and M. Resnick have contributed to the development of this theory. Supporters of Constructivism argue that the application of Behaviorism in the educational process promotes a teaching approach that is centered on the individual rather than teamwork. Constructivism is founded on five distinct stages, namely:

- Activating previously acquired knowledge
- Acquiring new knowledge
- Comprehending acquired knowledge
- Applying acquired knowledge
- Receiving feedback.

Piaget's primary theory posits that knowledge is not simply transmitted, but rather it is structured. As a result, the teaching process should establish the criteria through which students can acquire more cognitive skills. To achieve this, there must be active interaction between the teacher and students, as well as among the students themselves (Duckworth, 1964). Bruner's theory of discovery learning (1961) asserts that learning is a process that relies on trial, research, discovery, and reconstruction, through which individuals acquire knowledge. According to Bruner, mental development consists of three stages: enactive representation, iconic representation, and symbolic representation.

Constructivism is an educational and psychological theory emphasizing learners' active role in building their own knowledge and understanding of the world, rather than just acquiring it from external sources. This approach proposes that learners construct their own mental models based on their experiences and environment, instead of just absorbing information. Constructivists believe learners should be encouraged to ask questions, make connections, and reflect on their learning process to gain deeper comprehension. Key principles include learners constructing their own knowledge, building on prior knowledge, active learning through experience, and reflection on the learning process. Some key principles of constructivism include:

- Learners build their own knowledge and comprehension by experiencing and engaging with their surroundings.
- Learning involves active and creative processes, not just passively receiving information.
- Learners should be prompted to inquire, associate ideas, and contemplate their learning methods.
- Learning is a collective and cooperative process because learners develop understanding through collaborating.
- Teachers should facilitate by steering learners through learning and supplying chances to explore and uncover.
- Learning should relate to learners' experiences and interests.

While constructivism has been used in inquiry-based, project-based, and problem-based learning to foster active student engagement, some critics contend that it may

not sufficiently emphasize building foundational knowledge and skills or using external sources.

Humanism

Humanism is a philosophical and cultural movement that champions human dignity and potential over religious or supernatural authority. Humanists believe people can lead meaningful, fulfilling lives through reason, critical thinking, and individual freedom. This perspective has shaped Western culture, art, literature, politics, and education by stressing human ability, achievement, and progress. Humanism encourages individuals to actively shape their own lives and communities (David, 2015).

Humanism's perspective on education can be deconstructed into various fundamental principles. Firstly, it emphasizes the concept of free will, which implies that every individual has the liberty to make their own choices. Secondly, humanism believes in the innate goodness of human beings, which suggests that every person is inherently good and desires the best for themselves and others. Thirdly, it recognizes the importance of positive emotions in the learning process, as emotions and intellect are interconnected. Lastly, humanism asserts that intrinsic motivation is an inherent trait in humans, which drives them to strive towards becoming the best version of themselves.

Connectionism

Edward Thorndike's Connectionism Theory is based on the idea that learning occurs through the formation of associations between stimuli and responses. These associations, also known as habits, are strengthened or weakened depending on the nature and frequency of the stimulus-response pairings. The theory suggests that mental processes are a result of synaptic and neural activity, where information is processed through patterns of activation that spread throughout the brain. When information is received by the brain, neurons are triggered and form a distinct pattern, leading to a specific output and the creation of networks between neurons (Medler, 1998).

Connectionism proposes that the human brain processes information through interconnected neural networks rather than discrete symbolic rules. In connectionist models, information is represented and processed via the strength and direction of connections between nodes. This contrasts with traditional computational models relying on explicit rules or algorithms. Connectionism has been applied to cognitive tasks like pattern recognition, language, and memory.

Socialcultural Learning Theory

The sociocultural theories of learning posit that the acquisition of knowledge is shaped by social factors and occurs within environments where individuals engage in collaborative, communicative, and interactive activities. These theories were heavily influenced by Vygotsky's (1962) theory of social development, which emphasizes the crucial role of social interaction in the learning process. Vygotsky (1978) introduced the concept of the zone of proximal development (ZPD) to illustrate how social

interaction and learning contribute to the development of knowledge. Lave (1998) built upon this theory with her concept of Situated Learning, which asserts that learning is most effective when it occurs within a specific context and is supported by social and cognitive resources. Another variation of this theory is Cognitive Apprenticeship (Collins, Brown, & Newman, 1989), which suggests that learning can be optimized through guided practice and feedback from an expert educator who helps the learner achieve their goals.

According to Sociocultural Learning Theory, learning is not an individual process, but rather a collaborative one that is mediated by cultural tools and shaped by social contexts. This psychological theory emphasizes that we construct knowledge and meaning through dynamic social interactions within cultural settings. It proposes that language, symbols, beliefs, values, and other sociocultural factors fundamentally influence the learning process.

Sociocultural Learning Theory has several key principles, including:

- **Mediation:** Learning involves utilizing cultural tools like language, symbols, and artifacts to represent and transform knowledge.
- **Collaboration:** Learning occurs through social interaction and working together, allowing learners to jointly construct their understanding of the world.
- **Activity:** Learning requires active engagement as learners participate in meaningful, purposeful activities to build their own understanding.
- **Context:** Learning is influenced by social and cultural contexts including values, beliefs, and norms.
- **Development:** Learning builds on prior knowledge and experience to progressively construct new understanding.
- **Scaffolding:** More knowledgeable people facilitate learning by providing support and guidance to help learners build their own understanding.

The sociocultural theory of learning has significant implications for education, proposing that learning is inherently a social and collaborative process. This perspective indicates that optimal learning experiences should incorporate opportunities for social interaction and collaboration while also aligning with students' cultural contexts to ensure relevance and responsiveness.

In summary, Sociocultural Learning Theory offers a framework for understanding how learning happens through social and cultural contexts. It proposes that learning is an active, dynamic process facilitated by cultural tools, more knowledgeable mentors, and the influence of sociocultural environments. The concept of “developmental proximal zones” is central to sociocultural learning. This refers to the gap between what a person can do independently and what they can achieve with the guidance and support of others. Vygotsky believed that learning occurs most effectively when learners are given appropriate tasks that are beyond their current abilities. Sociocultural learning theory emphasizes the role of language and communication in cognitive development. Language serves as a tool for thinking, solving problems, and understanding the world around us, by interacting with more knowledgeable people, learners acquire new concepts and ideas, expand their vocabulary, and develop higher-order thinking skills. Another important aspect of sociocultural learning is the influence of cultural values, beliefs, and practices on the learning process.

Learning is not seen as a purely individual endeavor, but as a collective activity influenced by cultural norms and expectations. Cultural tools such as symbols, artifacts, and technology shape the way we learn and understand the world.

Overall, sociocultural learning theory emphasizes the importance of social interaction, cooperation, and cultural context in the learning process. We recognize that learning is a dynamic and social activity that occurs through meaningful interactions with others and within specific cultural contexts.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the main theories of learning in education provide valuable frameworks for understanding how individuals acquire knowledge, develop skills, and undergo personal growth through educational experiences. From behaviorism, which emphasizes observable behaviors and reinforcement, to cognitivism, which focuses on mental processes like memory and problem-solving, to constructivism, which highlights the active construction of knowledge through social interaction and reflection, each theory offers unique insights into the learning process. Additionally, transformative learning theories, such as Mezirow's theory, underscore the potential for profound shifts in perspectives and beliefs through critical reflection and self-examination. By integrating these diverse theories into educational practices, educators can create dynamic learning environments that cater to the diverse needs and learning styles of students, fostering engagement, critical thinking, and lifelong learning. Ultimately, a comprehensive understanding of these main theories of learning can inform effective teaching strategies, curriculum design, and support systems that promote student success and holistic development in educational settings.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Bandura, A. (2009). Social cognitive theory of mass communication. In J. Bryant & M. B. Oliver (Eds.), *Media effects: Advances in theory and research* (2nd ed., pp. 94-124). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Bruner, J. (1961). The act of discovery. *Harvard Educational Review*, 31, 21-32.
- Collins, A., Brown, J. S., & Newman, S. E. (1989). Cognitive apprenticeship: Teaching the crafts of reading, writing, and mathematics. In L. B. Resnick (Ed.), *Knowing, learning and instruction: Essays in honor of Robert Glaser* (pp. 453-494). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- David, L. (2015). Humanism in learning theories. *Learning Theories*. Retrieved from <https://www.learning-theories.com/humanism.html>
- Duckworth, E. (1964). Piaget rediscovered. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 2(3), 172-175. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.3660020306>

European Commission. (1995). *White paper on education and training: Teaching and learning – Towards the learning society*. Brussels: European Commission. Retrieved from https://europa.eu/documents/comm/white_papers/pdf/com95_590_en.pdf

Hiemstra, R., & Sisco, B. (1990). *Individualizing instruction for adult learners: Making learning personal, powerful, and successful*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

Kurt, S. (2023, October 25). Cognitivism learning theory, strategies and examples. *Educational Technology*. Retrieved from <https://educationaltechnology.net/cognitivism-learning-theory-strategies-and-examples>

Medler, D. A. (1998). A brief history of connectionism. *Neural Computing Surveys*, 1(2), 18-72.

Lave, J. (1998). *Cognition in practice: Mind, mathematics, and culture in everyday life*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511609268>

Pavlov, I. (1927). *Conditioned reflexes: An investigation of the physiological activity of the cerebral cortex* (G. W. Anrep, Trans.). New York: Dover Publications.

Rogers, A. (1999). *Η Εκπαίδευση Ενηλίκων* [Adult education]. Αθήνα: Μεταίχμιο.

Skinner, B. F. (1968). *The technology of teaching*. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts.

Thorndike, E. L. (1931). *Human learning*. New York: The Macmillan Company.

Tolman, M. N., & Hardy, G. R. (1995). *Discovering elementary science: Method, content, and problem-solving activities*. Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon.

Vygotsky, L. S. (1962). *Thought and language* (E. Hanfmann & G. Vakar, Trans.). Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Watson, J. B. (1924). *Psychology from the standpoint of a behaviorist*. Philadelphia: J. B. Lippincott Company.